

Agriculture Supply Chain Management Based on Blockchain Architecture and Smart Contracts

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ABSTRACT : The advent of Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) has spurred innovation across various industries, with Supply Chain Management (SCM) being one of the primary beneficiaries. Leveraging blockchain technology, SCM processes stand to undergo substantial improvements in efficiency, transparency, and traceability. In particular, the Food Supply Chain (FSC) has witnessed significant enhancements through the integration of blockchain, offering improved product traceability, streamlined coordination among stakeholders, and easier access to funding. This paper introduces FARMSUPPLY, a novel blockchain-based model tailored for the Food Supply Chain. FARMSUPPLY harnesses Ethereum blockchain technology and smart contracts to verify and validate critical attributes at each stage of the food supply chain. Through a comprehensive exploration of FARMSUPPLY's architecture and functionality, this paper elucidates its potential to revolutionize food supply chain management, offering stakeholders a clearer view of farmers, products, and retailers. By facilitating seamless data sharing, trust, and accountability across the FSC, FARMSUPPLY aims to enhance food safety, quality, and sustainability, thereby contributing to the optimization of global food supply chains.

Keywords: Distributed Ledger Technology, Blockchain, Supply Chain Management, Food Supply Chain, FARMSUPPLY, Ethereum, Smart Contracts, Traceability, Transparency, Food Safety, Sustainability.

I. INTRODUCTION

This project aims to modernize the Food Supply Chain (FSC) using Ethereum blockchain, with a primary focus on enhancing efficiency, transparency, and security. By leveraging Ethereum's capabilities, we aim to streamline FSC operations, provide stakeholders with clear insights, and fortify transactional security for a more reliable supply chain. Traditional FSC methods face challenges, including inefficiencies, a lack of transparency, and susceptibility to fraud. Manual processes hinder traceability and compliance verification. Our project addresses these issues, recognizing the need for a more effective and secure approach. To tackle the identified challenges, we integrate Ethereum blockchain and smart contracts. In our case, it's used to store information regarding product origins, verification processes, and authenticity checks. Blockchain functions as a digital ledger, maintaining a secure and transparent record of transactions. These blocks are distributed across multiple computers (nodes), making it much harder for anyone to tamper with the data or compromise the entire system. Blockchain offers several advantages. First, it's decentralized, meaning the data isn't stored in one vulnerable location. Second, it enhances security because the data is stored in encrypted format that's very difficult to alter or hack. Third, it promotes transparency, as all transactions are recorded and visible to authorized users. Fourth, it ensures data immutability, meaning once something is recorded in the blockchain, it can't be easily changed. Finally, it's resilient to failures because even if some nodes go down, others continue to maintain the data. This initiative capitalizes on Ethereum's blockchain, renowned for its smart contract capabilities. These contracts on the Ethereum network not only secure but also meticulously track critical product details, further elevating transparency and reliability in the supply chain.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

- 1. Block-chain Technology for Food supply chains:** The technology Block-chain is most emerging and widely used in almost all the applications like supply chain management systems, healthcare, banking industries, business, IT sectors, government organizations, agriculture etc. The food products are more sensitive, and it is very hard to trace the origin, buyers, sellers, farmers with the existing centralized method. The usage of Block-chain technology is proposed and experimented in this work along with the features of decentralization, increased security, immutability, and tamper proof for supply chains. The

proposed work uses the smart contract on Ethereum for food supply chain management systems, which avoids falsifying information, corrupting database, external attacks. The analysis of food supply chains is shown in the experimental results.

2. **A Comprehensive Review of Blockchain based Solutions in Food Supply Chain Management:** Lack of information on food produce such as origin, quality, shelf time etc. for the consumers has resulted in distrust among them which can also affect the producers in terms of marketing and pricing. All this stems from the current food procurement and distribution systems that are centrally controlled and dependence on regulatory bodies for quality control. This has led to opacity about information about the food produce and also doubts on such available data if any among the stakeholders. The need of the hour is a system that can provide information in a transparent manner to its stakeholders especially its customers. This information made reliably available will build trust among the consumers and thereby improves brand value for sellers. Block chain allows for generating trust among the stakeholders because of its properties like immutability and transparency that any one part of the system can verify the authenticity of information stored in it. If all transactions happening in the Food Procurement and Distribution system from point of production to the point of consumption are recorded on the Block chain. Then it becomes easier for customers to verify whether the claims from the seller about the food quality are indeed true. This paper outlines a survey on the current work and research in the field of food supply chain management using Block chain technology and also specify the future research trends in the same area.
3. **Blockchain-Based Agri-Food Supply Chain: A Complete Solution:** Supply chains are evolving into automated and highly complex networks and are becoming an important source of potential benefits in the modern world. At the same time, consumers are now more interested in food product quality. However, it is challenging to track the provenance of data and maintain its traceability throughout the supply chain network. The traditional supply chains are centralized and they depend on a third party for trading. These centralized systems lack transparency, accountability and auditability. In our proposed solution, we have presented a complete solution for blockchain-based Agriculture and Food (Agri-Food) supply chain. It leverages the key features of blockchain and smart contracts, deployed over ethereum blockchain network. Although blockchain provides immutability of data and records in the network, it still fails to solve some major problems in supply chain management like credibility of the involved entities, accountability of the trading process and traceability of the products. Therefore, there is a need of a reliable system that ensures traceability, trust and delivery mechanism in Agri-Food supply chain. In the proposed system, all transactions are written to blockchain which ultimately uploads the data to Interplanetary File Storage System (IPFS). The storage system returns a hash of the data which is stored on blockchain and ensures efficient, secure and reliable solution. Our system provides smart contracts along with their algorithms to show interaction of entities in the system. Furthermore, simulations and evaluation of smart contracts along with the security and vulnerability analyses are also presented in this work.

III. METHODOLOGY

1. **Blockchain-Based Platforms:** Developing dedicated blockchain platforms or networks for agriculture supply chains, Blockchain-based platforms are digital ecosystems that leverage blockchain technology to facilitate secure and transparent transactions, data sharing, and interactions among multiple participants. These platforms often provide a decentralized and distributed ledger that records and verifies transactions, offering benefits such as immutability, traceability, and enhanced trust by ensuring data integrity and reducing the need for intermediaries.
2. **Identify Use Cases:** Identify specific use cases within the agriculture supply chain where blockchain can bring value, such as tracking product origin, ensuring quality standards, or streamlining payments. Conduct interviews or surveys with stakeholders (farmers, distributors, retailers) to understand pain points and opportunities for blockchain integration.
3. **Design Smart Contracts:** Smart contracts are automated, self-executing agreements that operate on blockchain platforms, enabling stakeholders to securely participate and transact. These contracts automate the terms and conditions of an agreement, triggering actions like asset transfers when specific conditions are met. They improve transparency, security, and efficiency across industries such as finance, supply chain management, and decentralized applications. Smart contracts have the potential to reduce

fraud, lower transaction costs, facilitate trustless interactions, and minimize disputes, making them a revolutionary technology in numerous sectors.

- 4. Development and Implementation:** Select a technology stack based on your requirements (e.g., HTML/CSS, JavaScript, PHP, Python, content management systems like WordPress or Drupal). Develop the front-end (client-side) of the website, including the user interface, navigation, and interactive elements. Implement the back-end (server-side) functionality, such as database integration, user authentication, and data processing.

Fig 1: DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

- 5. System Architecture:** We are proposing the system using blockchain technology. we are going to use blockchain to store the user data and user transactions. Blockchain has one important feature that is once data or transaction is stored in the blockchain no one can delete or modify the data. our system users' data is going to store ganache blockchain. which is Ethereum based blockchain technology. once data is encrypted and stored in the blockchain. When someone tries to hack or modify the data inside the blockchain it is not possible. It increases data security in a decentralized manner.

Fig 2: SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The main advantage of blockchain is its special feature called transparency. so, what is this transparency means, in block chain each transaction one new block is created, and all those blocks are visible to everyone around the globe. Whereas native databases, each company should maintain a database, those databases are not safe from the hac, no transparency among the databases. Using blockchain can minimize the frauds fraud contracts in blockchain, helps in automating the process like a refund, verification of spoiled food, in such cases, when customer-submitted all the required files the claim is automatically approved and paid without any human interference.

Fig 3: CLASS DIAGRAM

IV. RESULTS

Fig 4: HOME PAGE

OrganicFarm Farmer Register Farmer Login Manufacturer Register Manufacturer Login Distributor Register Distributor Login Retailer Register Retailer Login Customer Register Customer Login

Add Farmer

Username

Password

Number

Email

Address

Fig 5: FARMER REGISTRATION

OrganicFarm Customer Screen Logout

Product Number	Product Name	Quantity in Kg	Product Price per kg	Comments by distributor	Photo	Action
103	Brinjal	100	60	100		Click Here to buy
101	tamato	200	20	200		Click Here to buy
102	carrot	100	50	100		Click Here to buy

Fig 6: CUSTOMER SCREEN

V. CONCLUSION

The integration of blockchain technology marks a transformative step in the food supply chain, redefining how information is exchanged and transactions are conducted among diverse stakeholders. Through the use of Ethereum smart contracts and a tamper-resistant blockchain, the project ensures secure crop tracing and transparent communications, bolstering the overall security and reliability of the supply chain. The project successfully eliminates the need for intermediaries, transaction records, and centralized authorities, embracing the decentralized nature of blockchain. This reduces dependency, lowers costs, and streamlines processes within the agricultural supply chain. The combination of an immutable ledger and the integration with the InterPlanetary File System (IPFS) creates a robust record-keeping system. Each piece of information is uniquely identified and linked, providing a tamper-resistant and permanent record of communications.

VI. REFERENCES

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